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Spatial Analysis of Urban Expansion on Ecologically Sensitive Areas in Lagos Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Urban expansion in Lagos, particularly in Eti-Osa, has intensified in recent decades, often encroaching on ecologically sensitive areas such as wetlands, mangroves, and coastal zones. This study applies spatial analytical tools—particularly Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Remote Sensing—to evaluate the extent and pattern of land cover change from natural ecosystems to built-up areas. Using a mixed-method approach that combines field surveys, spatial analysis, and stakeholder perspectives, the study evaluates the socio-economic characteristics of residents, their awareness of environmental issues, the drivers of ESA encroachment, and the resulting ecological impacts. Findings reveal that a majority of residents are middle-aged, well-educated, and economically stable, with a high level of awareness about the presence of ESAs, particularly wetlands. The research identifies hotspots of ecological disturbance, assesses the environmental implications, and recommends strategies for sustainable urban development that align with ecological preservation. However, land acquisition in the area is overwhelmingly dominated by private estate developers (80%), often at the expense of environmental sustainability. Key drivers of ESA encroachment include demographic and economic pressures, inadequate urban planning policies, and weak environmental governance. The most severe impacts identified are biodiversity loss, farmland depletion, and the degradation of ecosystem services, all of which pose long-term threats to ecological and human well-being. The study concludes by recommending integrated policy interventions that emphasize environmental governance, inclusive urban planning, protection and restoration of ESAs, and public awareness campaigns. These measures are critical to mitigating the negative consequences of unchecked urban growth and ensuring sustainable land use in Eti-Osa and similar urban environments.

Keywords: *Urban expansion, ecologically sensitive areas, land use, wetlands, spatial analysis, biodiversity loss*

INTRODUCTION

The global distribution of human population has shifted significantly, with 57% (approximately 4.6 billion people) residing in urban areas as of 2024, compared to 43% (about 3.5 billion) in rural areas (Dyvik, 2024). Africa is currently undergoing an unprecedented phase of urbanization, now outpacing the rapid urban growth experienced in East Asia during the late 20th and early 21st centuries [33]. Projections indicate that by 2050, nearly 68% of the world's population will be urban, with Africa's urban population expected to reach 1.4 billion [33,48,49]. While urbanization is driven by prospects such as employment, education, and improved healthcare [1], it also places immense pressure on infrastructure and the environment, often resulting in overcrowded settlements, inadequate public services, and significant ecological degradation. Urban expansion, defined as the physical growth of urban areas into surrounding rural or natural landscapes [50], frequently involves the conversion of forests, wetlands, and farmlands into built-up environments. This transformation disrupts ecological balance, particularly in developing regions like Africa where urban land cover is projected to triple, accompanied by declining urban densities [11, 20,21,22,23,39,45]. The unregulated spread of cities often leads to the degradation of ecologically sensitive areas (ESAs), resulting in loss of biodiversity, habitat fragmentation, and diminished ecosystem services [20,41].

ESAs are defined as landscapes, ecosystems, or sites critical to the long-term survival of biodiversity and the conservation of vital natural resources such as soil and water [46]. These areas provide crucial ecological services,

classified into four categories: provisioning (e.g., food, wood, fibre), regulating (e.g., carbon sequestration, pollution control), supporting (e.g., nutrient cycling, biodiversity conservation), and cultural (e.g., recreational, spiritual, educational) functions [40]. However, increasing urban encroachment into ESAs compromises their functionality and ecological integrity, especially in coastal cities like Lagos. In Nigeria, cities such as Lagos, Ibadan, Akure, and Abuja have experienced intense ESA degradation due to rapid and unplanned urban growth, leading to heightened flood risks, rising temperatures, and reduced environmental quality [2,8]. Remote sensing studies have documented significant losses in wetlands, forests, and other ecologically valuable landscapes [3,6,18,19,24,42]. Eti-Osa, located in the southeastern part of Lagos State, is a rapidly urbanizing region that includes high-profile areas like Victoria Island, Lekki, and Ikoyi. Despite its economic vibrancy, the area hosts several ecologically sensitive features such as wetlands, lagoons, and mangrove forests, which are increasingly threatened by unregulated land conversion. This poses serious risks to ecosystem services such as flood regulation and shoreline protection, which are essential to the sustainability and resilience of the region [14,16,25,26]. Consequently, this study seeks to examine the rate, magnitude, and drivers of urban expansion in Eti-Osa and its impact on ecologically sensitive areas. Utilizing geospatial technologies and machine learning tools, the research aims to generate spatially explicit data and analysis to inform sustainable urban planning. The goal is to support evidence-based policies that balance urban development with environmental

conservation, ensuring the long-term resilience of Eti-Osa and other rapidly urbanizing areas in Lagos.[17]

LITERATURE SEARCH

Empirical Literature Review on Urban Expansion in Southwestern Nigeria

Salam, (2023) highlighted that urban expansion in Southwestern Nigeria is characterized by the transformation of land into built-up environments, driven by factors such as population growth and increased economic activities. [44] This involves the conversion of previously undeveloped or agricultural land into residential, commercial, and industrial areas to accommodate the needs of a growing urban population. This process results in significant alterations to land use and land cover patterns, particularly in regions experiencing rapid urbanization such as Southwestern Nigeria [5]. As cities grow, they extend their boundaries, consuming adjacent land and reshaping the natural landscape. The dynamics of urban expansion are complex, influenced by a variety of factors including infrastructure development, transportation networks, and socio-economic opportunities. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for managing the environmental impacts associated with urban growth. The uncontrolled nature of urban expansion often leads to a host of environmental challenges, most notably the encroachment upon ecologically sensitive areas [27]. Without proper planning and regulatory frameworks, urban development can spread into regions that are vital for biodiversity, hydrological functions, and overall ecosystem health. This encroachment not only alters the physical landscape but also disrupts ecological processes, leading to habitat loss, water pollution, and a decline in ecosystem services. Thus, the challenge lies in balancing the need for urban development with the imperative of environmental conservation, ensuring that growth occurs

in a sustainable manner that minimizes harm to sensitive ecosystems. [4]

Ahmed and Taiwo, (2023) examined the impact of Ilorin Airport on land-use patterns in the Ilorin metropolis with the aid of remote sensing and GIS. [7] The research provides valuable insights into the complex interactions between infrastructure development and urban expansion. Their study highlights the importance of considering the environmental impacts of development projects and the need for sustainable land-use planning. The research contributes to a better understanding of the dynamics of urban growth in Southwestern Nigeria. The study revealed significant shifts in land use from 1972 to 2018, with increased built-up areas and decreased grassland due to airport growth and urbanization, demonstrating the direct impact of infrastructure development on land cover change. This shift in land use has had significant consequences for the environment, including the loss of habitat and the degradation of water quality. The study highlights the need for careful planning to mitigate the negative impacts of development projects. Oluwatimilehin, and Ayanlade (2022) assessed urban expansion and its effects on land surface temperature in Oyo town through the lens of remote sensing. [35] The study found that built-up areas increased significantly between 1990 and 2021, leading to higher land surface temperatures and the development of an urban heat island, demonstrating the direct impact of urban expansion on local climate [12,43]. This increase in land surface temperature can have significant consequences for human health, increasing the risk of heatstroke and other heat-related illnesses. The study highlights the need for urban planning strategies to mitigate the urban heat island effect. Owoeye & Akinluyi, (2018); Oyinloye, (2013) in their studies analyzed urban sprawl in Akure, the studies reveal a

rapid increase in built-up areas, highlighting the challenges of managing urban growth in a sustainable manner. [36,37,38] Their studies combined satellite imagery analysis with field surveys to understand the factors driving urban expansion, providing a comprehensive approach to studying urban sprawl. The satellite imagery analysis allowed the researchers to track the changes in land use over time, while the field surveys provided valuable information about the social and economic factors driving urban expansion. This combined approach provides a more complete picture of the dynamics of urban sprawl in Akure Town.

Global and Regional Trends in ESA Encroachment

The encroachment into Ecological Sensitive Areas (ESAs) has become a global environmental crisis, with varying patterns across different regions. Recent studies employing advanced geospatial technologies have revealed alarming trends. According to the World Resources Institute's 2023 Global Forest Watch report, which utilized Landsat and Sentinel-2 satellite imagery combined with AI-based algorithms, the world lost 11.1 million hectares of tropical forest in 2022 alone. [51] The Amazon Basin accounted for 43% of this loss, primarily due to agricultural expansion and illegal logging activities. The study employed a novel change detection methodology that combined spectral indices with temporal analysis to achieve 92% accuracy in identifying deforestation hotspots.

Urban Built Environment and ESA Encroachment

The relationship between urban growth and ESA degradation has become increasingly complex. A study in science used nighttime lights (VIIRS), Sentinel-1 radar data, and building footprint analysis to quantify urban expansion into ESAs across 500 cities worldwide. The research

revealed that medium-sized cities (1-5 million inhabitants) showed the highest proportional ESA encroachment at 42%, compared to 28% for megacities.

This finding was attributed to weaker planning regulations in rapidly growing secondary cities. Sun, et al., (2023) developed a new Urban Ecological Footprint Index (UEFI) that combines land surface temperature, impervious surface area, and habitat quality metrics derived from Landsat 9 and Planet Scope imagery. [47] Their analysis of coastal cities showed that reclaimed urban lands accounted for 39% of wetland losses globally. It concludes that sea-level rise mitigation projects often ironically destroy the very ecosystems that provide natural coastal protection. The phenomenon of "hidden urbanization" in ESAs has emerged as a critical research focus. Using high-resolution Maxar imagery and machine learning, a study identified previously undocumented settlement expansion within 1.5 km of over 83% of urban-adjacent protected areas. The study applied convolutional neural networks to detect informal structures in vegetated areas with 89% accuracy. This research fundamentally changed perceptions about the scale of ESA encroachment, showing official statistics underestimated the problem.

Ecological Area Encroachment in Nigeria: A Case Study

Ecological area encroachment in Nigerian cities has become a pressing environmental issue driven by rapid urbanization and weak regulatory enforcement. Ogunbode, Oyebamiji, Sanni, Akinwale, & Akinluyi (2025) reported that urban growth in cities like Lagos, Abuja, and Port Harcourt has led to the destruction of wetlands, forests, and floodplains, increasing flood risk and biodiversity loss. Poor land-use planning and corruption further contribute to the

illegal conversion of protected zones. GIS and remote sensing analyses confirm a significant decline in green spaces over the past two decades [31]. Informal settlements and infrastructure development are key drivers of habitat destruction. Olalekan & Eric (2022) found that urban sprawl in Lagos reduced buffer zones between 2010 and 2022, mainly due to agricultural and residential encroachment. [34] Similarly, Amadi, Youdewei, & Ogbuji (2021) noted that weak environmental law enforcement enables developers to build in sensitive areas. To address these issues, sustainable urban governance is essential. Enoguanbhor, Gollnow, & Walker (2021) advocate for integrating green infrastructure, enforcing zoning laws, and applying participatory mapping and penalties. [15] Obateru et al. (2024) emphasized the importance of public awareness and collaboration between government and communities. [30] Without immediate action, ongoing ecological loss will intensify climate risks and threaten urban sustainability in Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The Study Area

The Southwestern Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria comprises six states (Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Osun, Ondo, and Ekiti), located between latitudes 6°N and 9°N and longitudes 2°E and 6°E. Bordered by the Republic of Benin to the west, the Atlantic Ocean to the south, and other Nigerian geopolitical zones (North Central, South-South, and Southeast) to the north and east, the region features a mix of coastal plains, tropical rainforests, and derived savannah. It hosts major urban centers like Lagos (Nigeria's economic hub), Ibadan, and Abeokuta, with high population density and rapid urbanization. The zone is rich in biodiversity, including wetlands, mangroves, and forest reserves, but faces ecological pressures from urban expansion. Its tropical climate, with

distinct wet (April–October) and dry (November–March) seasons, supports agriculture, commerce, and industrial activities. Southwestern Nigeria is a region rich in history, culture, and economic significance. It is predominantly inhabited by the Yoruba ethnic group and comprises several key urban centers that have played vital roles in Nigeria's political, cultural, and socio-economic development (Figure 1). Eti-Osa is a prominent Local Government Area (LGA) located in the southeastern part of Lagos State, Nigeria. It comprises key urban districts such as Ikoyi, Victoria Island, Lekki, and Obalende, making it one of the most economically vibrant and rapidly urbanizing areas in the country. Strategically situated along the Atlantic coastline and bordered by the Lagos Lagoon, Eti-Osa is home to high-end residential, commercial, and governmental developments. Despite its urban prominence, Eti-Osa also hosts ecologically sensitive areas including wetlands, mangroves, coastal vegetation, and floodplains.

These ecosystems provide vital environmental services such as flood regulation, shoreline stabilization, and biodiversity conservation. However, the area's attractiveness for real estate development and population growth has led to intense land use conversion, often at the expense of these fragile ecosystems. In recent decades, Eti-Osa has witnessed rapid and largely unregulated urban expansion, which poses serious challenges to sustainable development. Issues such as flooding, habitat destruction, informal settlements, and loss of ecosystem services have become increasingly prominent. These conditions make Eti-Osa an ideal case for assessing the impacts of urban expansion on ecologically sensitive areas through spatial analysis (Figure 2). This summary explores the history, geographical background, climate,

topography, and population growth of these three cities, shedding light on their

individual characteristics and collective contribution to the region's development.

Fig. 1: Figure: Lagos State within the National Setting.
Source: ESRI, 2025.

Fig. 2: Map of Eti-Osa Showing Ecological Features.
Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Figure 2 shows the ecological and land use features of the Eti-Osa area in Lagos, Nigeria. It shows a multifaceted landscape where urban growth meets natural ecosystems. This reveals that urban areas are primarily in the central and western parts of the area, including sensitive places such as Victoria Island, Ikoyi, Lekki Phase 1, and Victoria Garden City. This shows significant urban development in these areas. Figure 1 also reveals that ecologically sensitive swamp forests cover the eastern and southeastern parts, particularly around Sangotedo and

Ogombo. These zones reveal the existence of significant wetland ecosystems. Water bodies, such as creeks and lagoons, are dispersed throughout the area. They shape natural boundaries and affect where settlements are located, predominantly in places like Ajah, Ikate, and Badore. Figure 1 also emphasises the Lekki-Epe Expressway as the main transportation route running north to south, which plays an important role in the urban development. This road links several communities and assists people's movement across the area. Side roads from

the expressway further improve access to residential and commercial areas like Royal Gardens Estate, Sangotedo, and Next Elegushi. This reveals a well-planned urban layout. The cohabitation of swift urban growth with environmentally sensitive zones highlights the need for cautious and sustainable planning. This is vital to ensure development does not harm the environment.

Data Collection Method

This study adopts a spatial and temporal analytical approach to assess the impact of urban expansion on ecologically sensitive areas in Eti-Osa, Lagos. The methodology integrates Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information System (GIS) tools to map, quantify, and analyze land use changes over a 25-year period (2000–2025).

The geographical boundary of Eti-Osa Local Government Area was obtained from the Lagos State GIS portal and validated using administrative shapefiles. The area encompasses key districts such as Ikoyi, Victoria Island, and Lekki, which are characterized by rapid urban growth and the presence of wetlands, lagoons, and mangrove forests. Satellite Imagery was acquired from the Landsat (TM, ETM+, and OLI) and Sentinel-2 archives for the years 2000, 2010, and 2025 (or latest available).

Ancillary Data such as topographic maps, vegetation maps, soil maps, and floodplain datasets were obtained from relevant agencies like the Lagos State Ministry of the Environment and international environmental databases. Primary source of data was obtained through socio-economic data collection from the site and evaluation of the ESAs in Eti-Osa. The satellite images underwent geometric correction, atmospheric correction, and sub-setting to the study area using ERDAS Imagine and ArcGIS Pro. This ensured

spatial consistency and clarity for accurate classification and analysis. A supervised classification technique using the Maximum Likelihood Algorithm was applied to classify the images into thematic classes, including: built-up area, water bodies, wetlands, vegetation and bare Land. Ground truthing and accuracy assessment were conducted using field surveys and high-resolution imagery from Google Earth. Post-classification comparison was used to analyze land use transitions between 2000, 2010, and 2025. This helped quantify the extent of urban expansion and identify specific ecological zones affected by the encroachment.

A sensitivity map was generated by overlaying classified land use maps with ecological layers (e.g., wetlands, floodplains, and vegetation cover). Buffer zones were created around key ecological features to assess degrees of encroachment and potential risk zones. GIS techniques including overlay analysis, buffer analysis, and hotspot mapping were employed to measure spatial extent of urban expansion, identify zones of environmental conflict, visualize patterns of urban growth relative to ecological boundaries and interpretation and Validation. The results were interpreted with reference to field observations, existing planning documents, and expert interviews. Validation of findings was performed using recent land cover datasets and feedback from local planning authorities.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Respondents

The analysis of respondents' socioeconomic characteristics as displayed in Table 1 revealed a predominantly male residents, with males accounting for 72% and females representing 28%. In terms of occupation, the majority (70%) were employed in the private sector, while smaller proportions were civil servants

(16%), traders (8%), and farmers (6%). Income distribution indicated that most respondents (68%) earned above ₦120,001 per month, whereas only 6% earned ₦30,000 or less, suggesting a sample with relatively high economic standing. Educational attainment was notably high, with 68% of respondents holding tertiary qualifications, followed by 24% with secondary education and 8% with basic education. Marital status data showed that 64% of respondents were married, 22% were single, and the remaining 14% were either divorced, widowed, or separated. Age distribution demonstrated that the largest group (52%) fell within the 46–59 age bracket, while individuals aged 60 and

above constituted the smallest proportion (4%). Religious affiliation varied, with Christianity being the most common (54%), followed by Islam (28%) and traditional beliefs (18%). Regarding residency duration, the majority (66%) had lived in the area for 11–20 years, while only 4% had resided there for 21–30 years. These findings suggest that the respondents were primarily middle-aged, well-educated, and economically stable individuals with long-term ties to the study location. The demographic composition may have implications for the generalizability of the study, particularly in contexts with different socioeconomic distributions.

Table 1: Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Respondents.

Characteristics	Frequency	Percent
Gender Classification		
Male	36	72.0
Female	14	28.0
Total	50	100.0
OCCUPATION		
Civil Servant	8	16.0
Trading	4	8.0
Private Employment	35	70.0
Farming	3	6.0
Total	50	100.0
INCOME		
Less than/ equal to ₦30,000	3	6.0
₦30,001 - ₦60,000	4	8.0
₦60,001 - ₦90,000	8	16.0
₦90,001 - ₦120,000	1	2.0
Above ₦120,001	34	68.0
Total	50	100.0
EDUCATIONAL STATUS		
Basic	4	8.0
Secondary	12	24.0
Tertiary	34	68.0
Total	50	100.0
MARITAL STATUS		
Single	11	22.0
Married	32	64.0
Divorced	1	2.0
Widowed	4	8.0
Separated	2	4.0

Total	50	100.0
AGE STRUCTURE		
18-30	9	18.0
31-45	13	26.0
46-59	26	52.0
60 Above	2	4.0
Total	50	100.0
RELIGION AFFLIATION		
Christianity	27	54.0
Islam	14	28.0
Traditional	9	18.0
Total	50	100.0
LENGTH OF STAY		
Less than 10years	11	22.0
11-20years	33	66.0
21-30years	2	4.0
31years Above	4	8.0
Total	50	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Ecological Sensitive areas Assessment and Land/Property Value

Figure 3 shows that 92% of residents are aware of ecologically sensitive areas (ESAs) in their environment, while only 8% are not. This high awareness may result from visible environmental changes, conservation efforts, or sustainability campaigns. Wetlands are the most recognized ESA (72%), likely due to their visibility and importance in coastal areas like Eti-Osa. Oceans follow at 22%, while urban forests (2%) and floodplains (4%) are less recognized possibly due to limited presence or visibility see Figure 4. These findings align with Ayanlade and Proske (2016), [13] who noted the prominence and vulnerability of Lagos wetlands. Private estate developers account for 80% of land acquisitions in the area, indicating strong private-sector influence in

urbanization, often at the expense of environmental protection. Government agency and family inheritance account for only 10% each as indicated in Figure 3, suggesting weak state control and declining traditional land tenure. This corroborate Nwokoro and Dekolo (2017) findings that developers often target wetlands, bypassing regulations. [28,29] Likewise, Ajayi and Adeleke (2019) also reported that urban growth is disrupting family-held land systems. [9,10] Regarding land prices, 80% of respondents rated them "Very High," 14% "High," and 6% "Moderate," reflecting inflated values driven by demand, location, and urbanization see Figure 4. Oduwaye and Okunola (2021) linked these trends to speculative markets that displace locals and harm ESAs. [32]

Fig. 3: Awareness of ESAs Availability
Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Fig. 4: Types of ESAs Available.
Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Fig. 5: Means of Land Acquisition.
Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Fig. 6: Land Purchase Price Category.
Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Drivers of Ecological Sensitive Areas Encroachment

Table 2 outlines the four ranked factors contributing to the encroachment of ecologically sensitive areas in Eti-Osa, Lagos. Demographic and economic factors (mean = 3.79) were identified as the leading cause, followed by infrastructure and urban policies (3.56), social and cultural influences (2.49), and environmental awareness and governance (2.23). The prominence of demographic and economic pressures affirmed the findings of Merem et al. (2018), which indicated that rapid population growth, urbanization, and industrial expansion as significant contributors to environmental degradation in Lagos, especially in coastal areas such as Eti-Osa, where land reclamation and unchecked development

heighten ecosystem vulnerability. Similarly, Olaifa et al. (2025) emphasized weak regulatory enforcement and economic incentives for coastal construction as key factors facilitating encroachment, supporting the high ranking of infrastructure and urban policies as major contributing factors. The lower scores for social/cultural influences and governance indicate a lack of community involvement and policy execution, aligning with studies on Lagos’s environmental issues, where top-down planning often overlooks local ecological knowledge and participatory governance. These findings highlight the necessity of integrated policies that address economic drivers while enhancing environmental governance and public awareness to reduce encroachment risks.

Table 2: Causative Factors for the Ecological Sensitive Areas Encroachment.

S/N	Factors	Mean	Rank
A	Demographic & Economic Factors	3.79	1 st
B	Infrastructure & Urban Policies	3.56	2 nd
C	Social & Cultural Influences	2.49	3 rd
D	Environmental Awareness & Governance	2.23	4 th

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Impacts of Ecological Sensitive Areas Encroachment

Table 3 illustrates the severity of ecological encroachment impacts in Eti-Osa, Lagos, with biodiversity loss (mean = 4.82) identified as the most critical

consequence, followed closely by urban farmland loss (4.68) and the loss of ecosystem services (4.59). These findings are consistent with studies documenting the rapid degradation of coastal ecosystems in Lagos due to urban

expansion and land reclamation activities. Merem et al. (2018) revealed that unchecked development in Eti-Osa led to significant habitat destruction, threatening endemic species and disrupting the ecological balance. Similarly, Tata (2024) observed that land reclamation for infrastructure projects in Lagos transformed wetlands and forests into built-up areas, exacerbating farmland loss and soil degradation. The high ranking of water pollution and scarcity (3.49) and socio-economic consequences (3.45) reflects the interconnectedness of environmental and human systems. Lawanson and Fadare (2015) noted that poor waste management and industrial

runoff in Eti-Osa contaminated water sources, affecting both aquatic life and local communities reliant on these resources. Although climate change effects (2.45) and health impacts (2.41) were ranked lower, they are emerging concerns. Odunuga et al. (2014) linked coastal inundation and rising temperatures in Lagos to increased respiratory diseases and heat stress, particularly in low-income neighborhoods. The study underscores the need for integrated policies that address both ecological preservation and urban planning. As demonstrated in similar studies, sustainable solutions, such as green infrastructure and stricter land-use regulations, could mitigate these impacts.

Table 3: Ecological Sensitive Areas Encroachment Impacts.

S/N	Factors	Mean	Rank
A	Biodiversity loss	4.82	1 st
B	Urban Farmland Loss	4.68	2 nd
C	Loss of Ecosystem Services	4.59	3 rd
D	Soil degradation and erosion	4.43	4 th
E	Water Pollution and Scarcity	3.49	5 th
F	Socio-Economic Consequences	3.45	6 th
G	Disruption of Hydrological Cycles	2.67	7 th
H	Climate Change Effects	2.45	8 th
I	Associated Health Impacts	2.41	9 th

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Land Use Changes in Ecological Sensitive Areas of Eti-Osa

Between 2005 and 2025, the Eti-Osa area of Lagos State, Nigeria, experienced changes in land cover, caused by rapid urbanisation and environmental degradation. In 2005, urban areas covered approximately 41.86 square kilometres, marking the commencement of notable expansion, mainly along the central and western parts of the area. Swamp groves were the dominant ecological feature at the time, spanning 74.51 square kilometres, while water bodies and marsh or barren land were 29.06 and 36.3 square kilometres, respectively. In 2010, urban land had increased to 53.06 square

kilometres, showing continued development as a result of infrastructure and population growth. However, this expansion comes with an implication, which has caused the swamp groves to decrease significantly to 42.39 square kilometres, signifying increasing pressure on sensitive ecosystems. Water bodies slightly decreased to 26.63 square kilometres, hinting at possible land reclamation efforts or encroachment. In 2015, urbanisation increased further, with urban areas up to 81.82 square kilometres. Swamp groves decreased to 29.19 square kilometres, continuing their downward trend, while marsh or barren land saw a modest increase to 41.71 square

kilometres. Water bodies also rose slightly to 27.75 square kilometres, possibly due to improved mapping or a false increase. Unexpectedly, in 2020, the urban area appeared to decrease to 39.23 square kilometres. This unexpected decrease was somehow linked to changes in classification approaches or updated mapping methods rather than an actual decline in development. During this period, swamp groves were reduced further to 15.64 square kilometres, and water bodies were also reduced to 15.63

square kilometres. Marsh or barren land, however, increased to 43.65 square kilometres, signifying a development of undeveloped or abandoned zones. In 2025, urban areas reached an unprecedented high of 107.53 square kilometres, highlighting intense urban development over two decades. Meanwhile, swamp groves had decreased extremely to 10.91 square kilometres. Water bodies somewhat recovered to 24.91 square kilometres, and marsh or barren land stabilised at 37.20 square kilometres.

Fig. 7: Showing Eti Osa in 2005.
Source: Field Survey, 2025

Fig. 8: Showing Eti Osa in 2010.
Source: Field Survey, 2025

*Fig. 9: Showing Eti Osa in 2015.
Source: Field Survey, 2025*

*Fig. 10: Showing Eti Osa in 2020.
Source: Field Survey, 2025*

*Fig. 11: Showing Eti Osa in 2025.
Source: Field Survey, 2025*

CONCLUSION

The findings from this study underscore the urgent need to address the growing tension between urban expansion and environmental sustainability in Eti-Osa, Lagos. As one of Nigeria's fastest-developing coastal districts, Eti-Osa is facing severe ecological stress due to unregulated land development, particularly in ecologically sensitive areas such as wetlands and floodplains. While awareness of these areas among residents is high, environmental governance and enforcement mechanisms remain weak, allowing private developers to dominate land acquisition and often bypass regulatory frameworks. The impacts of this encroachment are far-reaching. From biodiversity loss and the destruction of ecosystem services to the displacement of farmlands and increased vulnerability to climate risks, the degradation of ESAs threatens not only environmental health but also food security, livelihoods, and community well-being. The study highlights that demographic and economic pressures, coupled with poor infrastructure planning and governance gaps, are key drivers of this trend. To reverse this trajectory, an integrated policy response is essential—one that balances development with conservation. Strengthening environmental governance through the enforcement of zoning laws and environmental impact assessments is critical. Inclusive urban planning that values community participation and local knowledge systems will foster more equitable and contextually appropriate development. Furthermore, protecting and restoring ESAs, regulating land speculation, and raising public awareness must be prioritized to safeguard the ecological integrity of the area. Without immediate and coordinated policy interventions, Eti-Osa risks losing its environmental assets to short-term urban interests. A sustainable future depends on proactive planning, cross-sector

collaboration, and a deep commitment to preserving the natural systems that support urban life. Policymakers, planners, community leaders, and developers all have a role to play in shaping an urban landscape that is resilient, inclusive, and ecologically balanced.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Strengthening Environmental Governance

To mitigate the ongoing encroachment on ecologically sensitive areas (ESAs) in Eti-Osa, there is an urgent need to strengthen environmental governance frameworks. This begins with the strict enforcement of zoning regulations to ensure that land use aligns with sustainable development goals. Development should only proceed after thorough Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs) are conducted and approved, particularly in areas identified as wetlands, floodplains, or other environmentally fragile zones. Furthermore, monitoring mechanisms must be enhanced to track and regulate the activities of private estate developers who currently dominate land acquisition in the area. Strengthening oversight will help curb unauthorized developments and ensure that compliance with environmental standards is not only expected but enforced. Transparent accountability systems, possibly involving third-party audits or public reporting mechanisms, should be introduced to discourage violations and promote responsible land use practices. Ultimately, improving governance in the environmental sector will foster a more balanced approach to urban expansion—one that considers both ecological integrity and the long-term well-being of the local population.

Promote Inclusive Urban Planning

Inclusive urban planning is essential for ensuring that development in Eti-Osa reflects the needs, values, and priorities of the local population. One key strategy is to

actively involve community members in land-use decision-making processes. Local residents, who are often the most affected by changes in their environment, should have a voice in determining how land is allocated, developed, and preserved. Their participation not only enhances the legitimacy of planning efforts but also ensures that development projects are socially acceptable and culturally sensitive. Additionally, it is crucial to recognize and integrate traditional landowners and indigenous knowledge systems into formal urban planning structures. These local systems often carry deep historical and ecological insights that can support more sustainable and context-specific planning outcomes. By bridging the gap between informal, customary land tenure and formal planning mechanisms, authorities can foster greater cooperation, reduce land disputes, and preserve long-standing socio-cultural relationships with the land. Incorporating both modern urban planning techniques and traditional knowledge will create a more inclusive, equitable, and sustainable approach to managing Eti-Osa's rapidly changing landscape.

Protect and Restore Ecologically Sensitive Areas (ESAs)

Safeguarding the ecological integrity of Eti-Osa requires deliberate action to protect and rehabilitate its environmentally fragile zones, particularly wetlands, floodplains, and urban forests. These areas perform vital ecosystem functions such as flood control, water purification, and biodiversity conservation, and should be officially designated as green belts—zones where development is strictly regulated or prohibited. Establishing legal protection for these areas will help shield them from unchecked urban expansion and commercial exploitation. In addition to protection, there is an urgent need to restore ecosystems that have already been degraded due to land reclamation,

pollution, and illegal development. This can be achieved through nature-based solutions, such as reforestation, wetland rehabilitation, and the use of native vegetation to stabilize soils and improve biodiversity. Restoration initiatives should also engage local communities to ensure ownership, stewardship, and long-term maintenance of the restored areas. Protecting and restoring ESAs is not just an environmental imperative—it is a socio-economic necessity that ensures the sustainability of natural resources and the resilience of urban ecosystems in the face of climate change and continued population growth.

Regulate Land Markets

Unregulated land markets in Eti-Osa have contributed significantly to rising property values, speculative development, and the encroachment of ecologically sensitive areas. To counter these trends, policymakers should introduce land price control measures that help stabilize the market and prevent excessive inflation driven by private estate developers. In tandem, subsidies or incentives for environmentally sustainable development—such as green building practices or developments that preserve natural landscapes—can shift investor interest toward more responsible urban expansion. Moreover, the development of affordable public housing schemes is essential to reduce pressure on ecologically sensitive lands. By providing adequate and accessible housing alternatives, the government can minimize the demand for informal and speculative developments in protected zones. These interventions will not only promote social equity but also help balance the economic drivers of land use with environmental sustainability.

Raise Public Awareness

Public awareness and community engagement are critical components of any

effective environmental protection strategy. Sustained education campaigns highlighting the ecological, social, and economic importance of ESAs can foster a culture of conservation among residents and land users. These campaigns should be tailored to local contexts and disseminated through schools, media, community centers, and religious institutions to ensure broad reach and impact. Furthermore, partnerships with civil society organizations can amplify these efforts by promoting grassroots advocacy, organizing environmental stewardship programs, and ensuring community voices are included in policymaking. Engaged and informed citizens are more likely to support sustainable development initiatives, resist illegal encroachment, and actively participate in preserving their local environment. The encroachment on ecologically sensitive areas in Eti-Osa is a direct result of poorly regulated urban expansion. Sustainable urban development must balance growth with ecological preservation. Implementing integrated land-use policies, improving governance, and involving communities are key to safeguarding the environment and enhancing the quality of life for residents.

REFERENCES

1. Abubakar, I. R., & Dano, U. L. (2018). Socioeconomic challenges and opportunities of urbanization in Nigeria. *Urban Science*, 2(3), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/urbansci2030076>
2. Adelekan, I. O., & Asiyebi, A. P. (2020). Urbanization and the risk of climate-induced disasters in Nigerian cities. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 46, 101582. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2019.101582>
3. Adeleke, A. O. (2022). Wetland degradation in Lagos: Urban expansion and environmental policy failure. *Journal of Urban Studies and Development*, 18(1), 45–63.
4. Agrawal, A., & Redford, K. (2009). Conservation and displacement: An overview. *Conservation and Society*, 7(1), 1–10.
5. Ahmed, M. (2023). Dynamics of urban expansion in Southwestern Nigeria: A geospatial analysis. *Nigerian Journal of Geography and Environmental Planning*, 12(2), 23–38.
6. Ahmed, R., Meenar, M., & Alam, B. (2019). Monitoring land use changes and their environmental impact using GIS and remote sensing in Lagos, Nigeria. *Land Use Policy*, 82, 340–353.
7. Ahmed, R., & Taiwo, A. A. (2023). Assessing the impact of Ilorin Airport on urban land use using GIS. *Journal of Spatial Planning and Development*, 11(1), 33–47.
8. Ajayi, C. A., & Adeleke, O. M. (2019). Changing patterns of land ownership and their implications for sustainable urban development in Lagos, Nigeria. *Land Use Policy*, 87, 104049. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2019.104049>
9. Ajayi, A. A., & Adewumi, A. B. (2018). Land conversion and environmental degradation in urban Nigeria. *Environmental Management Review*, 16(3), 55–71.
10. Ajayi, A., & Adeleke, O. (2019). Urban expansion and family land systems: A Lagos case study. *African Journal of Sustainable Development*, 9(2), 82–98.
11. Angel, S., Parent, J., Civco, D. L., Blei, A. M., & Potere, D. (2015). The fragmenting of urban footprints: Evidence from global cities. *Environment and Urbanization*, 27(2), 381–407. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956247815608794>

12. Ayanlade, A. (2016). Sea Level Rise and Its Potential Impacts on Coastal Urban Area: A Case of Eti-Osa, Nigeria.
13. Ayanlade, A., & Proske, U. (2016). Assessing wetland degradation and loss of ecosystem services in the Niger Delta, Nigeria. *Marine and Freshwater Research*, 67(6), 828–836. <https://doi.org/10.1071/MF14260>
14. Elmqvist, T., Fragkias, M., Goodness, J., Güneralp, B., Marcotullio, P. J., McDonald, R. I., ... & Wilkinson, C. (2015). *Urbanization, biodiversity and ecosystem services: Challenges and opportunities*. Springer.
15. Enoguanbhor, E. C., Gollnow, F., & Walker, B. B. (2021). Sustainable land-use planning in Nigeria: Integrating green infrastructure. *Sustainability*, 13(8), 4207. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13084207>
16. Farley, J., & Costanza, R. (2010). Payments for ecosystem services: From local to global. *Ecological Economics*, 69(11), 2060–2068.
17. Foley, J. A., DeFries, R., Asner, G. P., Barford, C., Bonan, G., Carpenter, S. R., ... & Snyder, P. K. (2011). Global consequences of land use. *Science*, 309(5734), 570–574.
18. Gibbs, H. K., Ruesch, A. S., Achard, F., Clayton, M. K., Holmgren, P., Ramankutty, N., & Foley, J. A. (2010). Tropical forests were the primary sources of new agricultural land in the 1980s and 1990s. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 107(38), 16732–16737.
19. Goswami, R., Nautiyal, B., & Manasi, S. (2020). Urban expansion and environmental degradation in Lagos: A remote sensing-based analysis. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 263, 110388.
20. Güneralp, B., Lwasa, S., Masundire, H., Parnell, S., & Seto, K. C. (2020). Urbanization in Africa: Challenges and opportunities for conservation. *Environmental Research Letters*, 13(1), 015002.
21. Hall, C. M. (2021). Tourism and ecosystem services: An evolving agenda. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 29(5), 735–753.
22. IPCC. (2022). *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability*. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report. Cambridge University Press.
23. Korah, P. I., Koch, J., & Wimberly, M. C. (2024). Urban sprawl and ecological stress in African megacities. *Environmental Research Communications*, 6(2), 025008.
24. Kowe, A. T., Mutanga, O., & Dube, T. (2021). Monitoring urban land cover change in Lagos using Landsat imagery and machine learning. *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment*, 23, 100579.
25. Lambin, E. F., & Meyfroidt, P. (2011). Global land use change, economic globalization, and the looming land scarcity. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 108(9), 3465–3472.
26. McDonald, R. I. (2015). *Conservation for cities: How to plan and build natural infrastructure*. Island Press.
27. Merem, E. C. (2018). GIS assessment of the loss of green space and wetlands in Southern Nigeria. *Journal of Environmental Science and Engineering B*, 7, 1–20.
28. Nwokoro, I. (2022). *Gentrification and displacement in peri-urban Lagos: The Eti-Osa case*. Habitat International, 119, 102492. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2021.102492>

29. Nwokoro, I. I., & Dekolo, S. O. (2017). Urban sprawl and loss of wetlands in Eti-Osa, Lagos: The sustainability implications. *Journal of Urban Management*, 6(2), 45-59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jum.2017.05.001>
30. Obateru, T., Akintunde, O., Adewale, A., & Ogunbode, O. (2024). Community-based urban governance for environmental protection in Nigeria. *Urban Studies Journal*, 61(3), 505–523.
31. Obroma, E., Robert, L., & Lindsay, M. (2025). GIS analysis of land use changes in Nigerian urban centers. *African Journal of Environmental Studies*, 17(1), 90–107.
32. Oduwaye, L., & Okunola, O. (2021). *Speculative urbanism and land value inflation in Lagos' coastal communities*. *Journal of African Real Estate Research*, 6(2), 45-63.
33. OECD, UN-Habitat, & African Development Bank. (2025). *African Urbanization Outlook: Urban Trends in the 21st Century*. OECD Publishing.
34. Olalekan, T. A., & Eric, U. (2022). Urban sprawl and ecological risk assessment in Lagos. *Environmental Risk Assessment Review*, 10(4), 203–219.
35. Oluwatimilehin, A., & Ayanlade, A. (2022). Urban expansion and land surface temperature in Oyo town, Nigeria. *Urban Climate*, 41, 101013.
36. Ostrom, E. (2009). A general framework for analyzing sustainability of social–ecological systems. *Science*, 325(5939), 419–422.
37. Owoeye, J. O., & Akinluyi, F. O. (2018). Urban sprawl and sustainable city development in Nigeria: A case study of Akure. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 20(3), 112–129.
38. Oyinloye, M. A. (2013). Spatio-temporal pattern of urban sprawl in Akure, Nigeria. *Journal of Geography and Regional Planning*, 6(1), 1–8.
39. Owusu, M., Adjei, K. A., & Boateng, E. (2025). Mapping urban density and expansion in West African cities. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 93, 104585.
40. Pandey, R. (2020). Ecosystem services: Concept, classification and decision support tools. *International Journal of Ecology and Environmental Sciences*, 46(1), 1–10.
41. Rahman, M. A., Yuniarti, T., Ahmed, R., & Musa, H. (2023). Urbanization and ecological degradation in West Africa: Emerging challenges and responses. *Land Use Policy*, 125, 106398.
42. Remondi, F., Burlando, P., & Vollmer, D. (2016). Exploring the dynamics of urban growth and its environmental impacts: The case of Lagos, Nigeria. *Applied Geography*, 70, 34–49.
43. Salam, M. K. (2023). Urban growth and land transformation in Southwestern Nigeria. *Journal of Urban and Regional Planning*, 10(2), 65–78.
44. Salam, M. K., Oluwatimilehin, A., & Ayanlade, A. (2022). Urban heat island development in Oyo town: Implications for climate-resilient planning. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 194(12), 1–18.
45. Seto, K. C., Güneralp, B., & Hutyrá, L. R. (2012). Global forecasts of urban expansion to 2030 and direct impacts on biodiversity and carbon pools. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109(40), 16083–16088.
46. Srivastava, A., Scott, C. A., & Rosier, M. (2022). Identifying and conserving ecologically sensitive areas in the Global South.

- Environmental Conservation*, 49(2), 97–105.
47. Sun, Y., Chen, H., Wang, L., & Zhang, Z. (2023). Urban ecological footprint assessment using remote sensing: A global analysis. *Ecological Indicators*, 148, 110052.
48. Turner, M. G., Collins, S. L., Lugo, A. E., Magnuson, J. J., Rupp, T. S., & Swanson, F. J. (2020). Disturbance dynamics and ecological response: The contribution of long-term ecological research. *BioScience*, 70(1), 25–39.
49. UNDESA. (2022). *World Urbanization Prospects: The 2022 Revision*. United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs. <https://population.un.org/wup/>
50. United Nations. (2019). *World Cities Report 2018: The Value of Sustainable Urbanization*. UN-Habitat.
51. World Resources Institute. (2023). *Global Forest Watch: 2023 Annual Deforestation Report*. <https://www.globalforestwatch.org>